

UVA-PreCOVID

UVA-PreCOVID

UVA-PreCOVID: Budget k=2000

UVA-PostCOVID

UVA-PostCOVID

UVA-PostCOVID: Budget k=2000

(a) γ_{Loads} (b) γ_{Cases} (c) $Prob[Cases > Target]$